

The Musicians of Nebuchadnezzar as an Example of anti-Islamic Rhetoric in the Beatus Illuminations

RAQUEL JIMÉNEZ PASALODOS

Abstract

This article examines the illumination of the Babylonian musicians in the Beatus of Valcavado (970 CE) as a case study of anti-Islamic visual rhetoric in medieval Christian art. Focusing on the iconographic depiction of the musical ensemble described in Daniel 3:5, it explores how the illustrator Obeco selected specific instruments – such as the *albogue*, goblet drum, cymbals, and three-stringed lute – based not on biblical accuracy but on their symbolic associations with pagan, Islamic, and spirit-possession rituals performed in al-Andalus. Through detailed organological analysis and comparison with archaeological and iconographic sources, the study argues that these instruments were used to deliberately link the Babylonian idolaters with the contemporary Muslim lower classes. The article situates this imagery within broader political and cultural tensions between Christian and Islamic Iberia in the 9th–11th centuries, suggesting that the Babylonian orchestra functions as a theological and ideological critique of Islam, portraying it as an idolatrous and doomed empire. The study also considers Obeco's potential Mozarabic background as key to understanding his intimate familiarity with the instruments and their socio-religious connotations.

I musicisti di Nabucodonosor come esempio di retorica anti-islamica nelle Illuminazioni di Beatus. Questo articolo esamina la miniatura dei musicisti babilonesi nel Beato di Valcavado (970 d.C.) come caso di studio della retorica visiva anti-islamica nell'arte cristiana medievale. Concentrandosi sulla rappresentazione iconografica dell'ensemble musicale descritto in Daniele 3,5, si analizza come l'illustratore Obeco abbia selezionato strumenti specifici - come l'alboga, il tamburo a calice, i cimbali e il liuto a tre corde - basandosi non sull'accuratezza biblica ma sulle loro associazioni simboliche con i rituali pagani, islamici e di

possessione degli spiriti eseguiti ad al-Andalus. Attraverso un'analisi organologica dettagliata e il confronto con le fonti archeologiche e iconografiche, lo studio sostiene che questi strumenti sono stati utilizzati per collegare deliberatamente gli idolatri babilonesi con le classi inferiori musulmane contemporanee. L'articolo colloca questo immaginario all'interno delle più ampie tensioni politiche e culturali tra l'Iberia cristiana e islamica del IX-XI secolo, suggerendo che l'orchestra babilonese funziona come una critica teologica e ideologica dell'Islam, ritraendolo come un impero idolatra e condannato. Lo studio considera anche la potenziale formazione mozarabica di Obeco come chiave per comprendere la sua intima familiarità con gli strumenti e le loro connotazioni socio-religiose.

Introduction

The twelve books of the *Commentary on the Apocalypse* were written by the monk Beatus in 776, at the monastery of San Martín of Liébana, a village surrounded by mountains and one of the few territories that, at that time, remained under Christian rule following the expansion of the Umayyad Caliphate across the peninsula from 710. Although the original manuscript by Beatus did not survive, the work was copied and illustrated up until the 13th century. Today, 36 illuminated copies of the *Commentary on the Apocalypse* survive, dating from the 9th to the 13th centuries. In addition to these commentaries, from the 10th century onward, some codices also included Jerome's *Commentary on Daniel*. This work, which explains the Book of Daniel passage by passage, tells the story of the prophet Daniel in Babylon and features Daniel's prophecies concerning the End-times. Some of their biblical passages are particularly interesting from a musicological perspective and have been widely discussed (see for instance Moore 1905; Sachs 1940; Mitchell and Joyce 1965: 19-27; Dyer 1990; Braun 2002: 32-36). They contain the description of a Babylonian musical ensemble, listing various musical instruments in four different verses (Daniel 3:5,7,10, and 15). The copies of this commentaries were often accompanied by elaborate illuminations, but the first depiction of the Babylonian musicians appears in the Beatus of Valcavado¹ (9th century). This illumination is also of musicological interest, as the illustrator chose to depict a series of instruments that not only allow reflection on how the organological terms were interpreted in medieval times, but also on the symbolic and cultural associations of the instruments in 10th and 11th Centuries Iberia. In this article, I will first examine some interpretations of the musical instruments mentioned in the Book of Daniel. Subsequently, I will analyze how the Beatus illustrator might have understood the biblical list by examining other medieval written, iconographical and archaeological sources and I will delve into the reasons of his iconographical choices. Finally, I will attempt to interpret the meaning of this image by considering the cultural and political contexts in which it was created.

¹ The Beatus of Valcavado is also known as Beatus of Valladolid, because the codex is nowadays at the library of the University of Valladolid.

The Babylonian ensemble of the Book of Daniel

According to the biblical text, during Daniel's life in the Babylonian court, King Nebuchadnezzar ordered that a musical ensemble would play to force people to worship a golden statue erected by him. In Jerome's commentary, which copies the first lines of the biblical verses, the list of instruments is not fully enumerated.² However, in his translation of the Bible, the Vulgate – which was the most widely used Latin Bible in the Medieval Western Church – this passage is rendered as follows: «in hora qua audieritis sonitum tubae, et fistulae, et citharae, sambucae, et psalterii, et symphoniae, et universi generis musicorum, cadentes adore statuam auream, quam constituit Nabuchodonosor rex»³ (Daniel 3:5). Jerome's translation took into account the Masoretic text (William 1943). The Book of Daniel was likely composed in the 2nd century BCE, but the stories may have an older origin (Collins 1984: 34). Chapter 3, the tale of the fiery furnace in which these musical descriptions are included, is written in Aramaic, but the names of the musical instruments combine Aramaic and Greek terms. The Latin version is significantly accurate, as “tuba” is translated from the Aramaic “qarnā”, which is understood by scholars as some kind of horn and trumpet and fistula translates the term “mašrôqîṭā”, which is related to whistling sounds or shepherd's pipes (Mitchell and Joyce 1965: 23; Braun 2002: 33). The next three terms – “cithara”, “sambuca”, “psalteri” and “symphonia” – seem to be loans from Greek in the Aramaic version (Braun 2002: 33), and in the Vulgate are translated as “cithara”, “sambuca”, “psalterium” and “symphonia”.⁴ The translation and identification of some of the instruments pose challenges and several options have been proposed (Moore 1905; Sachs 1940; Mitchell and Joyce 1965: 19-27; Braun 2002: 32-36). The term “symphonia” is especially problematic. In modern translations, “symphonia” has frequently been translated as “bagpipe” or not translated at all. It may refer to some kind of reeded aerophone, as suggested by Moore (1905), it could merely mean a set of instruments playing simultaneously, as pointed out by Sachs (1940) and, more recently, Braun (2002), or it could even be a variation of the term “tympanon”, the Greek frame drum (Mitchell and Joyce 1965). Be it as it may, regardless of the exact meaning of the terms, the importance of this passage lies in the fact that it is the only instance in the Old Testament where non-Israelite instruments are mentioned. Braun suggests that

² *Commentarium in Daniele Prophetam ad Pammachium et Marcellam*, Liber Unus, Cap. III.4/5 and 7.

³ [«As soon as you hear the sound of the tuba, and fistula, and sambuca, and psalterium, and symphonia, and all kinds of music, you shall fall down and worship the golden statue erected by the King»] (the translation is mine).

⁴ Jerome took interest in the translation of the Hebrew and Aramaic musical instrument terms, and he accurately translates the passage according to the interpretations of modern scholarship. He also surely knew the translation of these terms to Greek both in the Septuagint and in Theodotion's translations of the Book of David. It is worth mentioning that, even if nowadays Jerome's authorship of the famous organological essay known as the Epistle to Dardanus, titled *De Diversis Generibus Musicorum*, is discredited (Meyer 2018), this medieval manuscript pays particular attention to the instruments of this Babylonian ensemble, and includes descriptions of the *tuba*, the *fistula*, the *cithara*, the *sambuca* and the *psalterium*. The earliest copies of this epistle date to the 9th Century, and it was recopied and illustrated throughout the Middle Ages at least 68 times.

this inclusion presents readers with a foreign (and possibly hostile) musical culture, at a time when the «[...] confrontation between the Jewish and Hellenistic cultures was becoming increasingly severe» (2002: 35).

If the identification of most of the musical instruments of the biblical text still poses challenges to both biblical translators and musicologists, it is quite likely that these terms did not have a precise meaning in 10th-century medieval Spain, when the first illumination of this musical scene was conceived. Even though previous manuscripts of the *Commentary on Daniel* were illuminated (cf. Morgan Beatus), the musical ensemble of the so called “Babylonian orchestra” is depicted for the first time on the upper half of fol. 199v of the Beatus of Valcavado, which dates to 970 (Fig. 1). The illuminator, a monk named Obeco, copied from previous codices the centre of the scene, a huge Babylonian idol flanked by prostrate worshippers, but distorted the pleasant image of the golden statue from the Morgan Beatus. He also added the representation of the musicians mentioned in the Book of Daniel, accompanied by the words *carmina musicorum* (“songs of the musicians”). The musical instruments depicted, from left to right, are an *albogue*,⁵ a pair of cymbals, an hourglass-shaped single-headed goblet drum, a doublepipe, a three-stringed long-necked lute, and a and a straight lip-reed instrument with conical bore. This miniature is also replicated in two later Beatus manuscripts, which exhibit modifications that suggest a limited understanding of the instruments of Obeco’s illumination: one from La Seu d’Urgell, dated to the late 10th century (circa 975, fol. 213v, Fig. 2), and another in the Beatus of Fernando I, dated to 1047 (fol. 275v, Fig. 3).

The illumination of this ensemble offers valuable insights into the medieval understanding of specific organological terminology and the cultural significance of these instruments, while also revealing the influence of the political context of his time, as the musical instruments depicted by Obeco do not fully correspond to those mentioned in the Hebrew, Greek, and Latin texts, nor to those listed in later medieval Spanish translations of the Bible. To understand the reasons behind this selection of instruments, it is essential to analyze them in detail. The representations of the trumpet and the lute are relatively straightforward. These two instruments appear in earlier Beatus manuscripts that Obeco used as models. In the Vulgate’s translation of the Apocalypse of Saint John, the “tuba” and the “cithara” are mentioned in several passages and were depicted in the Morgan Beatus as trumpets or horns (held by angels) and as lutes (held by the Elders), perhaps due to a misunderstanding of the original meaning. In Isidore of Seville’s *Etymologiae* (Book 3, XXI: 3), dated to the 7th century, and in the early Spanish biblical translations from the 12th and 13th Centuries, the term “tuba” is unambiguously iden-

⁵ Rosario Álvarez names this instrument with the Spanish term *albogue* (2007) that is a single-reed, single or double pipe instrument with a bell made from natural horn, although recognize its northern African affiliation. In this depiction, we can clearly see the intention of representing a cane with digitations and a separate bell with lines that suggest a natural horn. The latter miniature copyists misunderstood Obeco’s drawing and substituted the instrument for a simple horn (see Figg. 1, 2 and 3). Domenico Staiti also identifies this instrument as a North African clarinet (2021: 61).

tified as an aerophone that produces sound through lip vibration, which matches the instruments depicted in the codex. On the other hand, Isidore of Seville seems to understand *cithara* as the lyre from the Classical world (Book 3, XXII: 2-9), and in Spanish medieval Bibles, the term “cithara” is consistently translated as “cedra”,⁶ probably a not fully identified plucked string instrument that appears in written sources up to the 13th century, and could have been a kind of lute (Andrés 1995a). One possibility is that in Obeco’s time, or for his predecessors, it was indeed the name of a type of lute: this kind of instrument appears to have been adopted in Christian contexts, as evidenced by the fresco of an angel musician in the Romanesque church of San Miguel de Lillo (9th century, Fig. 4). However, these chordophones are more commonly found in both literary and iconographic Spanish-Arab medieval sources. The substitution of the *cithara* for a lute might be linked to the fact that the copyist of Obeco’s model, Maius, the illustrator of the Morgan codex, was a Mozarab – arabized Christian – (Williams 1994: 28-29), who chose to represent an al-Andalus chordophone, and, judging by its shape and number of strings, one that he probably knew from popular musical contexts, as the instrument is closer to the contemporary three-stringed North African *guembri* than the pear-shaped wooden lutes of al-Andalus aristocratic music (see, for instance, Figg. 5 and 6). In summary, Obeco maintained consistency with a previous copy of the Beatus by depicting long horns and trumpets (for the *tuba*) and popular North African lutes (for the *cithara*). The lute is the only chordophone from the biblical list represented by Obeco, as a depiction of the *psalterium* is lacking, even if Isidore of Seville described this instrument (Book 3, XXI:7), and there are iconographies contemporary to Obeco’s copy (Page 1977; Andrés 1995b). In Antiquity, the *psalterium* was generally a harp, but in the Middle Ages it was the name of different types of zithers (West 1992: 78).

Perhaps the Morgan Beatus depiction of the popular al-Andalus three-stringed large lutes inspired him to include the single-headed, hourglass-shaped drum (held upside down with the left hand and struck with the right hand). Membranophones are not mentioned in the biblical passage, although Rosario Álvarez believes that Obeco may have understood the term “symphonia” as such (1993: 217), arguing that Isidore of Sevilla describes the term as the common way of calling a double-headed wooden drum struck with beaters (Book III, 22: 10 and 15). However, it does not seem to be the instrument represented by Obeco, a small single-headed goblet drum struck with the hand. Although this type of instrument does not appear in elite Andalusian musical iconographies or listed in musical treatises, numerous similar drums made of pottery have been found in the archaeological record of al-Andalus. These archaeological membranophones are dated from the 8th-9th to the 14th centuries, and appear exclusively in territories under Islamic rule (Bill *et al.* 2013; Jiménez Pasalodos and Bill 2012 and 2016). Notably, the

⁶ *La fazienda de ultramar* (12th-13th century), translated from Hebrew: «bozinas, cedras, salterios, estiuas, simphonias, e todas maneras de cantar». Digital edition: Enrique-Arias 2008 (accessed on 02/03/2024).

latest archaeological example is the drum from El Castillejo de los Guájares in Granada, dating to the 14th century. The quantity and context of these findings suggest that these instruments were very common among the popular classes, which may explain their absence in aristocratic Arabic written sources and iconographies (Jiménez Pasalodos and Bill 2016). However, two examples of double drums can be found in 12th-century Almohad popular art. One example is the Tavira vase (Almohad Period, 12th century, Fig. 9), a ritual object featuring anthropomorphic and zoomorphic molded figurines, interpreted as depicting the ritual kidnapping of the Berber bride. Two of the figurines are shown playing musical instruments: a frame drum and a goblet drum. The other example is a beautifully crafted clay figurine of a drum player (Almohad Period, 1151-1300, Fig. 10) from Córdoba. The exclusive presence of goblet drum iconography in popular art further underscores the lower-class association of these instruments. These drums do not have any reflection in ethnographic instruments of the Iberian Peninsula, but just 14 kilometers away across the Strait of Gibraltar, such membranophones remain prevalent and are associated with both popular religious rituals of the Maghrebian Islamic tradition and spirit-possession and trance-performative practices (Isolabella and Jiménez Pasalodos 2019). It is very likely that their disappearance in al-Andalus was linked to the close association of the instrument with festivities of the Islamic calendar, and even with other types of spirit rituals of North-African origin performed by the lower classes (Isolabella and Jiménez Pasalodos 2019). Obeco depicted this drum with precise knowledge of its shape, size, and playing technique, along with associated instruments of probable North African origin, so he must have possessed personal familiarity with the instrument and was aware of its close association with popular rituals, as the drum is, as it has been previously stated, conspicuously absent from the Islamic iconographies of material goods circulating during that period. Even more, the context of this depiction, that of the adoration of a Babylonian false idol, distinct from the shared monotheistic God of the Abrahamic traditions, may even be alluding to trance and spirit-possession practices. The addition of this specific drum serves as evidence that Obeco had first-hand knowledge of the musical practices he was illustrating and was not merely copying musical scenes portrayed on imported goods in order to provide an oriental allure to the Babylonian landscape. In summary, it seems probable that the goblet drum was not an attempt to accurately represent any of the terms from the biblical list, but was deliberately chosen for its connection to popular musical practices among the lower classes of al-Andalus, those that the copyist was familiar with, and that probably included similar musical ensembles in both Islamic and Spirit-Possession rituals.

The interpretation of Obeco's choice of the *albogue* and the doublepipes also presents a significant challenge, as it is very difficult to ascertain which specific term from the biblical list he intended to exemplify. However, considering various medieval written sources, there are several possible interpretations. In his *Etymologiae* (7th century), Isidore of Seville indicates that the *fistula* was invented by Hermes, Pan or a Sicilian shepherd, and it

is very likely that Isidore knew the instrument was a type of pan flute.⁷ However, Isidore does not explain how the instrument works, and he places it just after the description of the *tibia* and the *calamus* (reed). Someone unfamiliar with the term could have also understood that the *fistula* was a reeded instrument. Also, in the same passage, Isidore seems to include the *sambuca* among the wind instruments (instead of its actual meaning of “harp”). To further complicate it, he explains that “*sambuca*” is a type *symphonia*, and the type of wood used to make *tibiae* (*Etymologiae*, Book 3, XXI-7).⁸ It is possible that Isidore assumed that a *sambuca* was a type of aerophone, deriving it from “*sambucus*”, elder bush, whose hollow stems were used for woodwind instruments. Even if his work dates from the 7th century, his ambiguous definition of “*fistula*”, “*sambuca*” and “*symphonia*” describing different types of wind instrument seems to continue until the 11th century. In the Latin-Arabic dictionary *Glossarium Latino-Arabicum*, “*symphonia*” and “*fistula*” have the same meaning, “*zām̄māra*”, and the translation of the term “*sambucus*” is “*zāmra*” (Seybold 1900: 197, 452, and 471). These terms have the root “*zmr*”, which in Semitic languages is used for musical instruments in general. However, *Zammāra* in Arabic is a usual term for wind instruments, and in some areas of the Arabic world, “*zummāra*”, “*zamr*”, “*zummāra*” or “*zumare*” are specific names of types of double clarinets which, like the “*arghūl*”, sometimes have a bell made of horn. Therefore, it is possible that Obeco understood these three terms, “*fistula*”, “*sambuca*” and “*symphonia*” as different types of instruments with reed mouthpieces, which would explain his choice for the *albogue* and the doublepipes. Moreover, in the *Glossarium* “*symphonia*” has a second possible translation, “*būq*”, from which the Spanish word “*albogue*” derives (“*al-būq*”, “the trumpet”), which was the term used to call a single reeded aerophone that uses a natural horn as a bell. In fact, the *Glossarium* includes the term “*tibia symphonia*”, which is translated into Arabic as “*būq*”. Consequently, it seems that in this 11th Century Latin Arab dictionary the three terms are used to describe a type of wind instrument, probably with reeds. This conclusion is further strengthened by the examination of a medieval Spanish translations of the Bible from Hebrew and Latin, *La fazienda de ultramar* (12th-13th Century). In the Book of Daniel, the terms “*sambuca*” and “*fistula*” are both translated by a single word, “*estiuas*” (cf. note 7). The term “*symphonia*” remains untranslated. The singular form “*estiuas*” is not a Spanish term currently in use, and I could not find other medieval sources using this word to name a musical instrument. However, it bears a resemblance to the Egyptian name for a type of *arghūl* (the Egyptian double clarinet) called “*stawiā*”. In Spanish, the liquid “*s*” at the beginning of a word is typically preceded by an “*e*” when followed by an occlusive, making it reasonable to think that the term describes a similar

⁷ «[6] *Fistulam* quidam putant a Mercurio inventam, alii a Fauno, quem Graeci vocant Pan. Nonnulli eam ab Idi pastore Agrigentino ex Sicilia. *Fistula* autem dicta, quod vocem emittat. Nam φώς Graece vox, στόλια missa appellatur.» (Lib.3, XXI-6, ed. W. M. Lindsay: *Isidori Hispalensis Episcopi Etymologiarum sive Originum libri XX*, Vol. 1. Oxford: Oxford University Press, Oxonii, 1911).

⁸ «[7] *Sambuca* in musicis species est symphoniarum. Est enim genus ligni fragilis, unde et *tibiae* conponuntur.» (Lib.3, XXI-7, ed. W. M. Lindsay).

instrument. Thus, the three instruments described in the Book of Daniel are likely represented in Obeco's work by two instruments: the doublepipe and the *albogue*.

Obeco's depiction of the *albogue* is very realistic, and more detailed than the one illustrated on the Abd al-Malik al-Muzaffar Ivory Casket, from Córdoba (1004-1005, Fig. 5), where an Islamic musician is shown playing alongside an *ūd* and a doublepipe, the one depicted on another 11th-century ivory casket, now housed at the Victoria and Albert Museum (Fig. 6), and also the one of the 11th Century Xativa basin (Fig. 11). His knowledge of the instrument shows that Obeco is again not merely copying Islamic iconographical models but knew the instrument himself. As far as doublepipes are concerned, they have been present on the Iberian Peninsula since Protohistory, but their representation in medieval times is scant, and it is difficult to assert that the instrument depicted was the double-reed instrument from the Classical world. The earliest known medieval example is the one on the already mentioned Abd al-Malik al-Muzaffar Ivory Casket, playing together with a lute and a doublepipe (Fig. 5). This doublepipe is very likely a reeded instrument, as despite the unusual position of the hands, the musician's inflated cheeks indicate the instrument required considerable air pressure. Once more, Obeco's choice of these aerophones might reflect an orientalist intention, associating the Babylonian court with some kind of reeded double pipes still in use in the Islamic kingdoms. However, there also exists an early Christian example of reeded doublepipes sculpted in a capital of Jaca Cathedral (Fig. 7), dated to the second half of the 11th century. In this capital, a masculine and a female figure are flanked by two erotes playing reeded doublepipes, with the air visibly retained in the musicians' cheeks. The Greco-Roman style of the erotes, the presence of the doublepipes and the dynamic depiction of the clothing and the water suggest that it is a copy of a late antiquity model (Álvarez 2003: 90). Thus, Obeco may not have chosen the doublepipe as an Islamic instrument to bestow an oriental character on the Babylonians, but rather to represent a pagan, pre-Christian cult. It is plausible that medieval monks had some knowledge of pre-Christian Roman musical iconographies through classical texts or remnants of Roman art. An interesting example of this is the reuse of a 2nd-century Roman sarcophagus as the coffin of King Ramiro II of Aragon (1086-1157), now in the church of San Pedro el Viejo, in Huesca, which features a tibia and a lyre (Fig. 8). The concept of portraying pagan Roman musicians to illustrate a passage where the Bible denounces the false adoration of an idol is further reinforced by Obeco's depiction of the cymbal player. Notably, cymbals are absent from the list of biblical instruments, and it is unlikely that Obeco thought that any of the biblical terms were referring to them. Even if cymbals were used during the Middle Ages, as evidenced by their inclusion in the *Cantigas de Santa Maria* by Alfonso X el Sabio (Cantiga 190), the dynamism of Obeco's cymbal player – the movement of the hair and clothing, and the positioning of the body – strongly evokes Greco-Roman representations. It is not surprising that in the two later copies the musician was completely altered, replaced by a static figure consistent with medieval aesthetics (Figs. 2 and 3). In sum, the combination

of a doublepipe player and this dynamic cymbal player can be interpreted as an intention to depict a pagan musical cult, thereby reflecting the idolatry of the Babylonians.

Oriental, Pagans and Muslims

Considering the previous analysis, Obeco's selection of instruments invites two interpretations. The first is that Obeco aimed to emphasize the oriental character of the Babylonian court by including instruments from al-Andalus, in line with other interpretations of some of his miniatures. This influence of Islamic motifs is particularly evident in the Beatus of Branch II, such as in the Morgan Beatus and, more especially, in this Beatus of Valcavado. Some scholars have noted Obeco's intention to imbue the Babylonians with an oriental character in other iconographic variations introduced in his illuminations of the Book of Daniel (Williams 1994). For example, in the depiction of Belshazzar's feast, Obeco altered earlier illuminations to show the sovereign in a semi-recumbent posture instead of seated on a throne, reflecting contemporary Muslim fashion (Williams 1994: 39-40). Additionally, the red and white painted horseshoe arches evoke the architecture of the Córdoba Mosque. In the same scene, Obeco also depicted a fan in the hands of a servant, further associating the Babylonian court with Muslim rulers. The fan appears to be a court attribute in al-Andalus, as evidenced by the al-Mughira pyxis from 968. Considering the political context of the time, a deeper analysis of Obeco's selection of Islamic references is warranted, but John Williams stated that «the proposition of an anti-Islamic, ideological use of imagery is made still more difficult by the fact that Christian culture shared the iconographic traditions associated with the Muslim world» (1994: 139). Thus, although the Beatus were copied in the Northern Iberian territories, many goods produced in al-Andalus were circulating in the North, and certain iconographic themes may have influenced the commentaries. Nevertheless, the general influence of Islamic iconographic themes does not explain Obeco's choice of musical instruments that were in use by the lower classes of al-Andalus, distinct from those represented in aristocratic art. The primary evidence supporting this idea is the inclusion of the goblet drum. As previously discussed, these instruments do not appear in iconographic scenes from imported products, which typically depict musical scenes in court or paradise settings, nor are they found in the archaeological contexts of Christian kingdoms. Thus, these are popular instruments that could not have influenced Christian iconographic subjects. The presence of this specific drum in the adoration of the Babylonian idol is not simply a replication of al-Andalus musical depictions or an orientalist identification of the Babylonians with the luxuries of the Islamic court. Instead, it represents a clear connection of this "idolater ensemble" with popular musical practices of the Islamic lower classes, which may even have included spirit-possession rituals (Jiménez Pasalodos and Bill 2016; Isolabella and Jiménez Pasalodos 2019), which Obeco may have known well if he was actually a Mozarab. The realistic depiction of the *albogue* and the North-African

three-stringed lute reinforces this hypothesis. Furthermore, the inclusion of cymbals and the doublepipe supports the argument by accentuating the pagan nature of the musical ensemble. These instruments are deliberately selected to evoke musical traditions that the Christian Obeco associated with idolatry, such as Islamic music, spirit-possession rituals, and Greco-Roman religious ceremonies. The conscious selection of these instruments underscores the intended portrayal of these musical cultures as antithetical to Christian values, and identifiable with the finally fallen Babylonian kingdom of the book of Daniel.

The anti-Islamic rhetoric in Obeco's Babylonian orchestra

Consequently, this depiction from the Book of Daniel serves as an explicit anti-Muslim statement. The text of the *Commentary* itself does not contain any anti-Islamic rhetoric, as it is based on pre-Islamic texts and was written during the reign of Silo, in the Kingdom of Asturias, a time of peaceful Muslim-Christian relations. However, the political context of the 9th and 10th centuries brought heightened confrontations and continuous conflicts between the Islamic and Christian kingdoms along their borders. Additionally, the persecution of Christians in the Arab kingdoms resulted in the migration of Mozarab immigrants (Arabized Christians) to the northern territories. In the 9th century, anti-Islamic literature flourished, with Muhammad being compared to the Antichrist.⁹ John Williams suggests that “the addition of an illustrated Daniel Commentary at this moment may well reflect an ideological motive. The text of the Commentary maintained its freedom from topical reference. On the other hand, the illustrations potentially offered possibilities for commenting on the Christian-Muslim confrontations” (Williams 1994: 132). Werckmeister also reflects on how the recurrent adaptations of Islamic motifs in early medieval Christian art are not merely artistic or stylistic influences derived from the coexistence of the two cultures, as assumed by some art-history scholarship (Grabar 1953: 312-19) but also a reflection of political confrontation (Werckmeister 1997: 101-7). This analysis proves Williams and Werckmeister further. Obeco could not modify the text of the *Commentary*, but his choice of musical instruments addressed a fundamental theological question: which kingdom is doomed to failure according to the Revelation of the Apocalypse? If Daniel's Babylonia was equated with the Caliphate of Córdoba, it was this Islamic kingdom that was destined for destruction. It now appears evident that Obeco's intention was not to accurately represent the biblical list of instruments nor to randomly select instruments when he did not understand their meaning. The identification of the Babylonians with the Muslims was neither merely stylistic nor aesthetic. The chosen instruments were intentionally representing pagan and idolatrous worship

⁹ In 854, Paulus Alvarus, dedicated the second part of his *Indiculus Luminosus* to an exposure of Muhammad as a type of Antichrist (Williams 1994: 131).

accompanied with music, one that Obeco must have experienced first-hand. The Muslims were equated with the Idolatrous Empire of Babylon, which was prophesied to fall.

Perhaps Obeco was a migrant Mozarab himself, if his knowledge of the clay drums and the lutes and his likely identification of the *sambuca*, *symphonia*, and *fistula* with some kind of *zummāra* (as noted in the Latin-Arabic *Glossarium*) are considered. Mozarabs frequently fled Muslim territories to join the monasteries in the North, especially in the second half of the 9th century.¹⁰ Obeco is thus repeating the strategy of the writer of the Book of Daniel, emphasizing the significant connection between musical instruments, ritual, and identity. If Braun suggested that the choice of Greek musical terms aimed to present readers with a hostile musical culture (Braun 2002: 36), Obeco's choice of pagan and North African instruments shows the same tactic. Moreover, Obeco's detailed and contextually aware representations suggest a deep familiarity with musical practices of the Islamic popular classes, and even possibly with other types of rituals involving trance and spirit possession, which further support the hypothesis of a Mozarab background.

In conclusion, this examination of a single musical scene demonstrates how musical instruments have been extensively used to convey complex cultural and political messages, both in antiquity (in the original Book of Daniel) and in the Middle Ages. The representation of the Babylonian musical ensemble from the Book of Daniel in the Beatus of Valcavado reveals a complex interplay of religious, cultural, and political influences. The illuminations not only reflect the biblical text to a certain extent but also incorporate contemporary musical depictions that update the meaning for its contemporary audiences, as this illumination likely provides an accurate portrayal of some popular al-Andalus musical instruments and ensembles. The inclusion of the al-Andalus *albogue*, cymbals, three-stringed lute, goblet drum, and doublepipe not only illustrates the oriental nature of the Babylonian court but also conveys a deeper message. Obeco's choice underscores anti-Muslim sentiment, aligning the Babylonian idolaters not only with the Islamic rulers but also with contemporary Islamic lower social strata. By identifying the Islamic kingdoms and their citizens with the biblical Babylonians, their ultimate destruction, as prophesied in the biblical text, is implied.

¹⁰ The possibility that the copyists were Mozarab immigrants has been widely debated. The Arabic comments in the margins of the text and the Islamic influence in the iconographies, particularly in the Beatus manuscripts of Branch II (such as the Beatus of Morgan or the Valcavado Beatus), serve as the primary arguments supporting this theory. (Williams 1994: 143-144). The identification of the musical instruments made here supports this argument further.

References

- Álvarez Martínez, Rosario
 1993 “La iconografía musical de los beatos de los siglos X y XI y su procedencia”, *Anuario del departamento de Historia y Teoría del Arte*, V: 201-18.
 2003 “La iconografía musical de la escultura románica a la luz de los procedimientos de trabajo: I: Jaca, puerta de las Platerías de Santiago de Compostela y San Isidoro de León”, *Revista de Musicología*, XXVI: 76-126.
 2007 “Incidencia de una forma de trabajo en la representación de los instrumentos musicales: la copia de códices en la Edad Media”, *Nassare*, XXIII/1: 53-86.
- Andrés, Ramón
 1995a “Cedra”, in *Diccionario de Instrumentos musicales: de Píndaro a J.S. Bach*, Barcelona, Bibliograf.
 1995b “Psalterio”, in *Diccionario de Instrumentos musicales: de Píndaro a J.S. Bach*, Barcelona, Bibliograf.
- Bill, Alexandra, Raquel Jiménez Pasalodos, and Carlos García Benito
 2013 “A Classification of Clay Drums from al-Andalus (9th-14th centuries AD)”, in Luca Bombardieri, Anacleto D’Agostino, Guido Guarducci, Valentina Orsi and Stefano Valenti (eds.), *SOMA 2012: Identity and Connectivity Proceedings of the 16th Symposium on Mediterranean Archaeology*, BAR International Series 2581: 1097-1104.
- Braun, Joachim
 2002 *The Music in Ancient Israel-Palestine. Archaeological, Written, and Comparative Sources*, Michigan, Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Company.
- Collins, John J.
 1984 *Daniel, with an Introduction to Apocalyptic Literature*, Michigan, B. Eerdmans.
- Dyer, Charles H.
 1990 “The musical instruments in Daniel 3”, *Bibliotheca Sacra*, 147/588: 426-436.
- Enrique-Arias, Andrés (dir.)
 2008 *La fazienda de ultramar. Biblia Medieval*, online at: <<http://www.bibliamedieval.es>> (accessed on 02/03/2014).
- Grabar, André
 1953 “Éléments sassanides et islamiques dans les enluminures des manuscrits espagnols du haut moyen âge”, in Edoardo Arslan (ed.), *Arte del primo milenio: Atti del II Convegno per lo studio dell’arte dell’Alto Medioevo, Pavia 1950*, Torino, Viglongo.
- Isolabella, Matías, and Raquel Jiménez Pasalodos
 2019 “From Mud to Music: The Production and Uses of Clay Drums in Morocco”, *Etnografie Sonore/Sound Ethnographies*, II/2: 147-57.
- Jiménez Pasalodos, Raquel and Alexandra Bill
 2012 “Los tambores de cerámica de al-Andalus (ss. VIII-XIV): Una aproximación desde la Arqueología Musical”, *Nassarre: Revista Aragonesa de Musicología*, XXVIII: 13-42.
 2016 “Music and Identities Al-Andalus Clay Drums and the Study of Popular Musical Behaviors Through the Archaeological Record”, in Ricardo Eichmann, Jinjuan Fang, and Lars-Christian Koch (eds.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie X: Klang, Oject, Kultur, Geschichte*, Rahden, Verlag Marie Leidorf: 83-102.
- Meyer, Christian
 2018 “L’Epistola ad Dardanum. Le texte et sa tradition”, *Revista Internazionale di Musica Sacra*, XXXIX: 9-49.

- Mitchell, T. C. and R. Joyce
 1965 “The Musical Instruments in Nebuchadnezzar’s Orchestra”, in D. J. Wiseman (ed.), *Notes on Some Problems in the Book of Daniel*, London, The Tyndale Press: 19-27.
- Moore, George F.
 1905 “Συμφωνία Not a Bagpipe”, *Journal of Biblical Literature*, XXIV/2: 166-75.
- Page, Christopher
 1977 “Biblical instruments in Medieval Manuscript Illustration”, *Early Music*, V/3: 299-309.
- Sachs, Curt
 1940 *The History Of Musical Instruments*, New York, Norton & Company.
- Seybold, Christian Friedrich (ed.)
 1900 *Glossarium latino-arabicum, ex unico qui exstat codice Leidensi undecimo saeculo in Hispania conscript*, Berlin, Ae. Felber.
- Staiti, Domenico
 2021 *Tenui Meditabor Harundine. Tiritera su titiri, totare, tituelle, calamauli e cerauli*, Palermo, Edizioni Museo Pasqualino.
- Werckmeister, Otto Karl
 1965 “Islamische Formen in spanischen Miniaturen des 10. Jahrhunderts und das Problem der mozarabischen Buchmalerei”, *Settimane di Studio del Centro Italiano di Studi sull’Alto Medioevo*, XII: 933-67.
 1997 “The Islamic Rider in the Beatus of Girona”, *Gesta, International Center of Medieval Art*, XXXVI/2: 101-107.
- West, Martin L.
 1992 *Ancient Greek Music*, Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- William, Newton
 1943 “Influences on St. Jerome’s Translation of the Old Testament”, *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly*, V/1: 17-33.
- Williams, John:
 1994 *The Illustrated Beatus: A Corpus of the Illustrations of the Commentary on the Apocalypse*, London, Harvey-Miller.

FIGURE 1. Beatus of Valcavado, fol. 199v (detail). 970. Biblioteca Histórica de Santa Cruz, Universidad de Valladolid.

FIGURE 2. Beatus of Seu d'Urgell, fol. 213v (detail). C. 975?. Facsimile edition by Testimonio Compañía Editorial, Madrid (2004).

THE MUSICIANS OF NEBUCHADNEZZAR

FIGURE 3. Beatus of Fernando I, fol. 275v (detail). C. 1047. Facsimile edition by M. Moleiro Editores, Barcelona (1994).

FIGURE 4. Fresco of the angel musician. San Miguel de Lillo. 9th Century. Consejería de Educación, Cultura y Deporte. Principado de Asturias. Photo: Jesús Puras Higuera.

FIGURE 5. Detail of the musicians of Leyre Casket (Abd al-Malik al-Muzaffar Ivory Casket). Museo de Navarra, Pamplona.

FIGURE 6. Ivory Casket. 1000-1025, altered in the 17th or 18th Centuries. © Victoria and Albert Museum, London.

FIGURE 7. Capital from the San Pedro Cathedral, Jaca. Second half of 11th Century. Photo: Antonio García Omedes.

FIGURE 8A. Roman sarcophagus, 2nd-3rd Century a.C, containing the rests of the king Ramiro II of Aragon (12th Century). Church of San Pedro el Viejo, Huesca.

FIGURE 8B. Detail of the tibia player.

FIGURE 9. Tavira's vase. Museu Municipal de Tavira. Photo: António Cunha.

FIGURE 10. Almohade musician. Photo: Museo Arqueológico y Etnológico de Córdoba.

FIGURE 11. Detail of Xativa Bassin. Museo de Almodí, Xativa.

